

IMMER-CV: Curriculum development for Management of Immersive technologies by Professionals in Cultural and Creative Sectors

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Co-creation Workshop Guidelines

The main objective of the IMMERCV project is to train cultural managers and professionals in the use of immersive technology, so that they can effectively face the challenges posed by digital transition. An essential requirement to achieve this objective is foster partnership between diverse artistic professionals (e.g., cultural curators, art creators, digital managers, etc). For this reason, the co-creation workshop aims to create an open collaborative space for discussion between the stakeholders with the aim of framing current problems, defining sectoral needs, contributing with good ideas and, finally, being able to co-create satisfactory and up-to-date solutions.

Target group:

- 5-6 art professionals/art curators/professors/cultural managers
- 3-4 postgraduate students enrolled in master programs or similar.

Resources required:

- Wide space.
- Paper, pens and/or electronic devices
- Blackboard, screen or projectors.

Agenda: duration between 1,5-2 hours

Co-creation workshop programme	Duration
Introduction to the objective of the session and presentation of the participants	10 minutes
A brief overview of the current challenges	20 minutes
Defining sectoral needs	20 minutes
Brainstorming of ideas	25 minutes
Co-creating solutions	30 minutes
Conclusions and Closing session	10 minutes

1. Introduction to the objective of the workshop and presentation of the participants

The workshop will start with a brief presentation of the IMMERCV project, the aim of the study (i.e. identify user's needs and develop

vocational training solutions to improve their skills in the use of immersive technology in the artistic and cultural field) and the introduction of the participants. Participants will be asked to share personal information i.e. their name, surname, occupation and role in the company, field of expertise, company of employment, and if they have some experience using immersive technology in their field. This process will allow participants and workshop managers to get to know each other better and facilitate the discussion.

2. A brief overview of the current challenges - Empathy Map

In the beginning of this session, the workshop managers/facilitators will present successful use-cases of the application of immersive technology in the cultural field (either extended reality or other immersive experiences). Then they will initiate a discussion about problems already identified in other contexts in relation to training plans in immersive technology applied to the cultural and artistic sector.

Method: Participants will meet in two separate groups initially only with peers (students with students, cultural managers with cultural managers...). During these sub-group discussions, participants are requested to present the problems faced by their sector in the application of immersive technology from their viewpoint in order to discuss with the whole group at a later stage. To guide this step, you can use the questions described below based on an Empathy Map (Fig. 1) adapted to the context of the Workshop.

This step can be done in an introductory way, highlighting some important questions to provide a general overview of the emerging issues and the current state of the CCI environment.

- Guide questions tailored to Art Managers (AM), Students (S) or both (B):
 - What do they **think and feel**:
 - B: Do you have the necessary skills to apply immersive technology in your field, in your opinion? Please scale from 1 (Not at all) to 10 (Yes).
 - B: Have you ever received any training on VR, AR or any other immersive technologies? If so,
 - What frustrations have you encountered when you are trying to learn these immersive technologies?
 - Did you identify any gaps/topics missing in your training?
 - B: Do you think that the current educational curriculum available at training schools, universities, institutes,

seminars, etc. is satisfactorily adapted to new technologies? And why? Please scale from 1 (Not at all) to 10 (Absolutely)

- AM: Do you feel that art practitioners are sufficiently qualified to apply immersive technology nowadays? Explain why. Please scale from 1(Not at all) to 10 (Absolutely)
- S: Do you feel confident that after completing your studies you will have acquired the required knowledge and skills to apply immersive technology? Scale from 1 (Not at all) to 10 (Absolutely).
- What do they **see**:
 - B: Do you know of any practical examples of the use of immersive technology in your field?
 - B: Have you participated/attended/watched any immersive technology shows? What were your thoughts about the use in immersive technologies in the art sector?
 - B: Have you ever seen any immersive training plans and/or curriculums announced for the cultural and artistic field? Would you be interested in participating? Please scale from 1 (Not at all) to 10 (Absolutely).
- What do they **say and do**:
 - B: During conversations with your colleagues about the use of immersive technology in the CCI sector,
 - have you ever talked about the lack of information as an important problem?
 - what other issues did you discuss, e.g., pros and cons, artistic results, etc.?
 - S: Do you think that you and your peers have the necessary resources to be adequately trained in immersive technology?
 - AM: Do you think that students and future art practitioners have access to the necessary resources to be adequately trained in immersive technology?
 - B: Did you take any initiatives to learn/train about immersive technology?
- What do they **hear**:
 - B: Have you received recommendations of courses or training programs in immersive technologies? If yes,
 - Do you think they are suitable for the arts or cultural sector?
 - B: Do you know people from your sector, who have been trained in the use of immersive technologies or

people in general, who have participated in similar projects? If so,

- Do you know what their experience was like?

- Fig. 1. Empathy map

Outcome: to have an overview of the main issues and general perception of the participants. Each sub-group should fill this Empathy Map and share their point of view with the whole group of participants in order to identify commonalities and differences. The workshop managers will collect all empathy maps and formulate a final one.

3. Defining sectoral needs - Map of Needs

Based on the previous step, this section will identify the specific needs of users to have the necessary competences to apply and successfully use immersive technology in their fields.

Method: Creation of a Map of Needs to summarise the specific needs of the different stakeholders. This activity can be carried in two separated groups. Each group will discuss what competences or training they need to effectively apply immersive technology. The questions and table below can serve as a guide for the activity:

- To facilitate the process, the following questions can be asked:
 - B: What kind of training do you think you need to effectively apply immersive technology in your field?

- o What kind of training do you think you need to supervise the application of immersive technology in your field?
- o B: What resources would help you to improve your competences in the use of immersive technology?
- o B: What kind of training do you think would be most useful (specialised courses, further training, practical training, on-line courses, etc.)
- o B: What skills do you think that need to be improved to use immersive technology in your field?
- o B: What resources do you think you would need to create an adequate training plan applied to your field or work/study?
- o B: What kind of institutional support do you think you would need to be able to carry out this training?

For example, you can follow the table below:

Write your current field of expertise....

Write the sector in which the activity is carried out.....

Category	Description	Priority (high, medium, low)
Training needs		
<i>Specialised courses</i>	Training programmes focused on immersive technology applied to art or culture.	
<i>Practical training</i>	Workshops and activities that offer a real experience in the use of immersive technology	
<i>General training</i>	General (Theoretical) knowledge of the available tools and the use of immersive technology.	
Resources needs		
<i>Spaces for experimentation</i>	Spaces where technology can be experimented with	
<i>Technical support</i>	Technical assistance in the training process	
<i>Up-to-date technology</i>	Have the latest technology available	
<i>Online tutorials</i>	Available on-line tutorials on how to use immersive technology	
Competence requirements		

<i>Technical skills</i>	Technical skills for using immersive technology	
<i>Management skills</i>	Training in the planning and executing projects integrating immersive technology	
<i>Creative skills</i>	Training in the creation of cultural/artistic content integrating immersive technology	
Support and collaboration needs		
<i>Education funding</i>	Scholarships/Opportunities to financially support training	
<i>Institutional partnerships</i>	Communication between educational, cultural and technological institutions.	
Need for information		
Information about new technologies	Access to information on emerging technologies and their application	
Information spaces	Informative spaces on new cases, application of immersive technology in art or culture.	
<i>(Please indicate any others that you think are important)</i>		

Each group will rate each priority accordingly. Once they have finished, the groups will share those needs they have identified as high priority, and a list will be compiled. This will provide an overview of the main needs of the participants in immersive training and capacity building.

Outcome: have a visual map that can serve as a guide for finding solutions.

4. Brainstorming of ideas - Brainwriting Technique

Based on the Map of Needs and the identification of problems, ideas will be provided with the aim to design training plans that meet the needs outlined above.

- Methodology:

Brainwriting technique: each participant (or group) starts by writing 3 ideas (based on the needs outlined above) on a piece of paper in 5 minutes. Then, they pass it to the partner (or group) on the left, who must write 3 more ideas based on the ones they have just received. Several rounds take place and once finished, each participant (or group) must read out the ideas on their card to select the best ideas and, by voting, the participants choose which ones the organisation should work on.

- For example, you can follow the questions below to guide the process based on the “How might we” technique:
 - o How might we manage collaboration between artists, cultural managers and technical staff to improve training?
 - o How might we make a training plan flexible enough to meet the needs of each artistic-cultural sector?
 - o How might we ensure that the training programme addresses both technical and creative aspects?
 - o How might we create experimental spaces for immersive technology?
 - o How might we ensure that stakeholders are properly informed about the training modules?
 - o How might we ensure that the immersive training plan is adapted to the (artistic-cultural) knowledge of the participants?
 - o How might we develop an immersive training plan that enhances the previous skills of the participants?
 - o How might we ensure information on new application cases of immersive technology?

Brainwriting Table

Category	“How might we”	Ideas
Training needs	Ex: how might we make a training plan flexible enough to meet the needs of each artistic-cultural sector?	
Resource needs	Ex: how might we create experimental spaces for immersive technology?	
Competence requirements	Ex: how might we ensure that the training programme addresses both technical and creative aspects?	

Support and collaboration needs	Ex: how might we collaborate between artists, cultural managers and technical staff to improve training?	
Need for information	Ex: how might we ensure information on new application cases of immersive technology?	

Outcome: Come up with clear ideas that respond to the needs of the sector to continue to provide workable solutions.

5. Co-creation solutions - Building a suitable curriculum per module

The workshop will end with the design of a training plan according to what has been discussed above (problems and needs). This activity can be carried out in mixed groups. The activity can be carried out using digital platforms (e.g., PowerPoint, MiroBoard) or on paper.

- **First step:** participants will be divided into mixed groups and will have to design a module or training plan according to the competence or training they have identified as missing in the previous sessions. The idea should include name of the module, objective, importance, type of training, duration, competence to be developed and format.
 - You can use these questions to guide the process:
 - Should we learn how to use immersive technology technically or is it more important to know how to integrate the technology into a creative process?
 - Should it focus more on general training, or on specialised courses?
 - Should it be more theoretical or practical, or both?
 - Should it focus on a specific sector, or can it apply to all those related to culture/art?
 - Should other types of competences, such as the “soft skills”, be incorporated?
 - Should it be delivered online, face-to-face or blended?
 - You can use the following table:

Table Curriculum Development per Module

Module	Module development
Name of the module	
Aim of the module	
Relevance of the module	
Training type	
Competence developed	
Duration	
Format	

- **Second step:** feedback in real time. Each group presents its module or training plan to the other participants. After the presentation, a short questions-and-answers session is opened with an emphasis on the feasibility of the proposal in a real context and how it could be applied in practice.
- **Last step:** final discussion. After the presentations, the groups will be able to adjust their prototypes, based on the recommendations they have received.

Outcome: get an insight into what the main stakeholders need to be properly trained in immersive technology. In this way, the proposals can serve as a guide for the design and implementation of future training modules.

6. Closing session

The closing will be followed by a final reflection on how the solutions that have emerged will guide future work and be adapted to the needs of users.

- Final questions:
 - What did you learn in the workshop?
 - What is the most important thing that you took away from this experience?

7. Final evaluation

At the end of the workshop, a survey of all participants will be conducted. This survey should reflect the satisfaction and learning experienced in the workshop. For example, here are some of the questions that the survey can include:

- Questions to identify the user (respecting the anonymity of the user)
- Age

- Current work situation
 - Self-employed
 - Employee
 - Retired
 - Unemployed
 - Student
 - Unpaid domestic work
 - Other:

- Personal experience with the use of immersive technology in the arts
 - Fairly experienced
 - Experienced
 - Little experienced
 - No experience

- Field in which the activity is or has been carried out
 - Cultural heritage organisations and museums
 - Cultural and arts organisations
 - Creative industries professionals
 - Local and regional authorities
 - Other:

1. General valuation of the workshop

- Please, rate on a scale of 1 to 5, where 1=very dissatisfied; 2=dissatisfied; 3=neutral; 4=satisfied; 5= very satisfied, the following aspects of the workshop:
 - Organisation
 - Quality
 - Usefulness of the activities
 - Relevance

- Would you participate in this or similar workshops again?
 - Yes
 - No
 - I don't know / Maybe

- How did you feel sharing your ideas and experiences with the group?
 - Very comfortable
 - Comfortable
 - I don't know / I prefer not to answer
 - Uncomfortable
 - Very uncomfortable

- Prior to attending the workshop, had you planned or attended any training modules on the application of immersive technology in your field?
 - Yes, I had thought about it but I hadn't attended.
 - Yes, I had attended.
 - I wasn't sure. / I didn't find it interesting.
 - No.

- Did attending this workshop motivate you to learn more about the use of immersive technology in artistic creation or cultural management?
 - Yes
 - No
 - I don't know / Not sure.

- Do you have any suggestions for improvement for future editions? If yes, please write it below:

- How would you describe your experience at the workshop (you can select more than one option)?
 - Enriching
 - Innovative
 - Confusing
 - Boring
 - Motivating
 - Collaborative
 - Useful
 - Useless
 - Other:

- Do you feel that your ideas were considered during the workshop?
 - Yes, totally
 - Yes, sometimes
 - A few times
 - No
 - I don't know

2. Co-creation solutions.

- How much do you think immersive technology can enhance the experience in your field?
 - A lot
 - Somewhat
 - A little
 - Not at all

- Do you think that the solutions created adequately reflect the training needs discussed?
 - Yes, absolutely
 - I am still undecided
 - Somewhat
 - Not at all

- Do you think that the training plans presented can be implemented in your domain?
 - Yes, totally
 - Yes, but with some adjustments
 - Not at all
 - I don't know

- How do you rate the co-created solutions?
 - Very innovative
 - Effective
 - Innovative, but needs further development
 - Promising
 - Not very relevant
 - I don't think it is useful
 - I don't know

- Please, rate on a scale of 1 to 5, how useful you think the co-created solutions are:
 - 1= not useful at all
 - 2= not very useful
 - 3=neutral
 - 4=useful
 - 5=very useful

Finally, do you have any suggestions you would like to share about the workshop, or the activities carried out?

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